

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B250
Date: 30 November 2006
Take Off: 10:21:35
Landing: 15:28:33
Flight Time: 5h06m58

Campaign: NEON

Operating Area: East Anglia and North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
8	IR Camera	James Bowles	Met Office
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Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b250
 Date: 30 Nov 06
 Project: NEON
 Location: East Anglia / North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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095827		inu	-.03 kft	128	to navigate
095955		!	-.03 kft	128	HORACE recording ok
100018		!	-.03 kft	128	DRS status ok
102135		T/O	-.04 kft	211	Cranfield
102419		Video	4.6 kft	029	#1 spotter #2 IR camera
103819		Radar	11.0 kft	071	recording
104226		Nev	11.0 kft	097	zero
104339		JW	11.0 kft	140	zero
104927	110458	Profile 1	10.1 - -.12 kft	219	
110141		!	1.8 kft	223	30K +10 +8 Wattisham report
110934		H	0.34 kft	088	cal 7
111226	111246	Run 1.1	0.32 - 0.36 kft	053	
111635		H	0.45 kft	289	cal 7
111905	111931	Run 1.2	0.34 - 0.39 kft	222	
112209		H	0.83 kft	202	cal 7
112537	112558	Run 2.1	0.85 kft	031	
113019	113047	Run 2.2	0.88 - 0.87 kft	204	
113304		H	2.9 kft	245	cal 7
113647	113716	Run 3.1	2.9 kft	024	
113730		H	2.9 kft	026	cal 6
114343	114410	Run 3.2	2.9 kft	215	
114725		H	4.9 kft	063	cal 6
114831		Video	4.9 kft	037	#3 spotter #4 IR
114903	114926	Run 4.1	4.9 kft	029	
115649	115725	Run 4.2	4.9 kft	205	
120207	120229	Run 4.3	4.9 kft	030	
121040	121108	Run 4.4	4.9 kft	205	
121532		H	10.0 kft	067	cal 6
121751	121815	Run 5.1	10.0 kft	031	
122630	122703	Run 5.2	10.0 kft	205	
123259	123331	Run 5.3	10.0 kft	035	
123454		H	10.0 kft	041	cal 6
124913	130458	Profile 2	10.0 - -.04 kft	224	
125304		!	6.6 kft	227	35 k +10 +07 1028 101
125737		!	3.8 kft	223	40k +10 +7 1027 1016 Wattisham
130522		H	0.28 kft	217	cal 7
130937		H	0.45 kft	066	cal 7
131205	131227	Run 6.1	0.46 - 0.51 kft	055	
131725	131751	Run 6.2	0.48 - 0.45 kft	222	
131909		H	0.98 kft	224	cal 7
131942		Video	0.94 kft	225	#5 spotter #6 IR
132401	132417	Run 7.1	0.94 - 0.95 kft	030	
133239	133315	Run 8.1	5.0 kft	060	
133915		H	2.8 kft	259	cal 7
134025	134054	Run 9.1	2.8 kft	251	
134527	134549	Run 9.2	2.8 kft	153	
135023	135100	Run 9.3	2.8 kft	316	
135453	135535	Run 9.4	2.8 - 2.9 kft	104	
135729	135744	Run 10.1	0.62 - 0.61 kft	245	
135807		H	0.62 kft	247	cal 7
140106	140121	Run 10.2	0.66 - 0.65 kft	124	
140500	140536	Run 10.3	0.65 - 0.64 kft	259	
140907		!	0.68 kft	098	
141525		Video	0.64 kft	255	#5 fwd #6 down
141601	141634	Run 10.4	0.64 - 0.69 kft	243	
141704		Video	0.65 kft	253	#5 spotter #6 IR
142042	142121	Run 10.5	0.60 - 0.65 kft	110	

142550	142620	Run 10.6	0.68 - 0.66 kft	250	
143140	143205	Run 10.7	0.63 - 0.61 kft	109	
143407		!	1.3 kft	110	cloud
143652		H	2.8 kft	275	cal 7
144011	144057	Run 11.1	2.8 kft	280	
144519	144546	Run 11.2	2.8 kft	101	
144818		Video	2.8 kft	321	#7 spotter #8 IR
145028	145132	Run 11.3	2.8 kft	248	
145634	145731	Run 11.4	2.8 kft	129	
152833		Land	0.06 kft	213	Cranfield

B250 Track 30-NOV-06

SORTIE BRIEF

Flight B250 (NEON flight during WINTEX)

30th. Nov 2006

Trial Objectives

To validate the NEON TDA using the IR camera looking at a runway.

- Almost identical to previous NEON sorties during VISURB and CAPEX, but without Heiman-ARIES-loops (as ARIES not available before Christmas)
- measurements under different (winter) atmospheric conditions intended

Take off

10:30 local

Location

Over and nearby a runway (Wattisham Airfield).

Weather

Ideally: Totally cloud free conditions, flights around lunch time.

Instrumentation Required

IR camera, core temperature, water vapour, Heimann, aerosol instruments (PCASP)

Special Conditions + Hints

- Note that in order to keep the runway in the field of view of the IR camera all altitudes will need to be flown at exact heights above the surface and not at flight levels.
- Try to get the same part of the runway in the FoV at every altitude.
- Try to keep a roughly constant roll angle (ideally near zero) when taking photos of runway or ships.
- Important: Get information on **ground-based visibility** at the time of profiling from the airfield

Flight Pattern (see Fig. 1)

1. Take off and transit to airfield/runway, to arrive at 10,000ft.
--- Over/nearby runway-----
2. 1st PROFILE = descent at 1,000ft/min to minimum altitude (if possible with a missed approach at the operating airfield)
3. Two runs at 500ft, sequence: over and along runway, loop, displaced to runway over grass/ravel path next to runway; Heimann to look down on runway or grass respectively
4. 20-degree approaches (see Fig. 3), i.e. straight and level runs at 1000ft, 3000ft, 5000ft, and 10,000ft (getting the runway into the field of view of the IR camera)
5. 2nd PROFILE, identical to point 2 (if possible include another missed approach at the operating airfield)
6. repeat point 3

7. [Extra tasks, e.g. search a larger ship (e.g. a tanker) + fly at altitudes of 1000, 3000, 5000 and 10000ft above the ship, thereby getting the ship in the field of view of the IR camera

8. Transit back.
9. Landing.

Total time: about 3 hours for NEON + extras

NEON Sortie WINTEX

V/P = "fast" vertical profile
M/A = missed approach over runway
HAL = "Heimann-ARIES loop"

Fig. 1: NEON sortie Height vs. Time. It includes:

- Two vertical profiles (scientific flying), if possible ending with missed approaches
- Several "20-degree approaches" (cp. Fig. 3) at 1000, 3000, 5000, and 10,000ft.
- The two HALs (Heiman-ARIES-loops, as flown at earlier NEON missions) were crossed out and are substituted by points 3 and 6 in the flight pattern description.
- "Extra Tasks": time can be used for whatever project to use the maximum flying time.

“20-degree approach” - top view -

Fig. 3: “20 degree approach” instead of flying parallel to the runway to get runway in FoV of the IR cam.

!!!! IR camera

- Get runway in FoV of the IR camera during the 20-degree approaches (cp. Fig. 3), check using spotter camera. **If this fails, run must be repeated!**
- Record both, IR camera and spotter camera pics.

Appendix A: Height – Distance Conversion

The horizontal shift S of flight legs parallel to the runway to keep the runway in the view of the IR camera is dependent on the angle Y the camera is looking below the horizontal and the flight height H:

$$S \text{ (nautical miles)} = H \text{ (ft)} / \tan(Y) * 0.3048 * 0.54E-03$$

Assuming IR camera view = 35 degrees down the horizontal:

(Use EXCEL sheet to compute distances for other angles, <http://metresearch.net/CAESAR/>)

Ideal NEON flight levels marked with an X	Flight Height (ft)	Displacement right of runway (nautical miles)	Flight Height (km)	Displacement (km)	Displacement (statute miles)	IR camera viewing distance (km)
missed approach: X	0	0	0	0	0	0
X	500	0.118	0.152	0.218	0.135	0.12
X	1000	0.235	0.305	0.435	0.270	0.53
	2000	0.470	0.610	0.871	0.541	
X	3000	0.705	0.914	1.306	0.811	1.59
	4000	0.940	1.219	1.741	1.082	
X	5000	1.175	1.524	2.176	1.352	2.66
	6000	1.410	1.829	2.612	1.623	
	7000	1.645	2.134	3.047	1.893	
	8000	1.880	2.438	3.482	2.164	4.25
	9000	2.115	2.743	3.918	2.434	
X	10000	2.350	3.048	4.353	2.705	5.31
	12000	2.821	3.658	5.224	3.246	
(X)	14000	3.291	4.267	6.094	3.787	7.44
	27000	6.346	8.230	11.753	7.303	

Table 1: Displacement for straight and level runs to keep the runway in the FoV of the IR camera (Y=35 degrees).

Fig. 4: Displacement graph (Y=35 degrees).

Mission scientist de-brief

B250 NEON flight
30th November 2006

Mission scientist: Clare Lee

This NEON flight was successful in the runway measurements, however the ship chasing proved extremely difficult with the narrow field of view lens on the IR camera.

Weather conditions:

7/8 to 8/8/ thin cirrus cloud with no cloud below throughout the whole flight in the operating area. There was a very gradual thickening of the cirrus throughout the flight, however for the period of the runway science the changes were not large. The wind was S/SW'ly.

Visibility, temperature and dew point readings were taken from Wattisham air traffic controller several times during the flight.

Sortie:

A profile descent from 10,000ft was made ending with a missed approach at 50ft over Wattisham runway. The profile was made without interruption for turns and hence started some distance from the airfield. Due to the meteorological conditions, the air mass in the whole operating area should be very representative of that directly over Wattisham.

Runs at 500ft were made over the runway and then over the grass to the right hand side of the runway for the Heimann to measure the surface temperature. The IR camera was also operated during these runs. Runs were then made at 1000ft, 3000ft, 5000ft and 10000ft displaced from the runway, such that the IR camera could measure the grass and runway with a 20 degree approach. Two good measurements at each level were ensured by repeating runs when appropriate. Heimann and core chemistry calibrations were made at each run level. Some air traffic problems were encountered when requesting to go from 5000ft to 10,000ft, so the opportunity to do an additional run was made, whilst waiting for clearance.

A profile descent from 10,000ft was then made in the same manner as the first one. A second set of 500ft runs first over the runway and then over the grass was made. A further 1000ft 20degree approach run was made to ensure a full data set.

The aircraft ascended to 5000ft for transit to the sea for ship measurements. A large anchored ship was identified as a suitable target. With the narrow field of view of the IR camera this proved difficult, particularly with the additional requirement of being straight and level so that the measurement angle would be 30 degrees. It became apparent that the "stationary" target was drifting with the currents and hence unpredictable in its position. As other ships passed through the area opportunities were taken to measure these instead. During this exercise the IR camera managed to capture one good image and 2 partial images of ships. A full set of measurements at different altitudes was not possible and hence the task was aborted. Towards the end of the flight over the sea, small Cu clouds started to penetrate the operating area from the East and would have interfered with measurements if the flight had continued.

During one of the ascents during the ship task the aircraft passed through several of the Cu puffs to test the FFSSP.

Instrument problems:

TWC – gave no data

2DC – generating masses of data and filling up the disk drive, hence switched off during the flight.

Mission scientist laptop – problems with the mouse and lack of connection to Horace
– flight manager laptop used by the mission scientist instead.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B250** Date **30/11/06** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **1** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
102135					T10 Cranfield.
					818 thin mid + high cloud.
1035		11000ft.	097		Transit - In distance patch Ci ~ 418 Patches of very small W around in clumps
114927	P1st	10000ft.	219	52°26'N 1°36'E	Profile → soft at Waltham During descent small puffs W to N+NW Gears down during descent.
105039					Waltham Vis: 22km 700 broken 22kft 818 Ci above $W_{alt} = +10, +9 = 20$
1058		4000ft.	225		718 Ci Above. Wind 18ms ⁻¹ / 195°
110120					Vis: 30km T = +10/+8 (Waltham) 1019 QFE Waltham
110450	P1end	50ft.	227	52°05.9'N 1°00'E	End profile. Wind: 7197 T/T ₀ = 9 / 7 °C.
110530					Gear up.
110931		500ft.			low chem + Heiman cal. in left hand turn. T/T ₀ = 8.34 / 6.41 Wind: 14ms ⁻¹ / 186° 818 Ci overhead v. thin.
11224	R.1-4	500ft.	052		Over runway
11245	R.1end	500ft.			End runway
1113		1000ft.			Going up to 1000ft to turn around.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.250** Date **30/11/06** Name **CAARE LEE** Page **2** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					786 ahead otherwise clear
111710		500ft.	244	52°5.9'N 10°0'E	Heading back towards runway.
111905	R1.2	500ft.	244		Over grass beside runway. IR camera should see grass on other side, pan + aircraft sheltered
111931	R1.2end.	500ft.			Run end, then climb out.
112537	R2.1s	1000ft.	031		Run displaced from runway 20° Approach.
112558	R2.1E	1000ft.			End run
					wind: 18 / 171°, T/TD 7.3/4.9
113019	R2.2s	1000ft.	203		Run displaced from runway (20° approach)
113047	R2.2e	1000ft.	202		End run. climb to 3000ft. Heirloom + camera started
113647	R3.1s	3000ft.	024	52°5.9'N 0°53.9'E	Run displaced from runway (20° Approach) T/TD = 8.06 / -29.9°
					wind: 18ms ⁻¹ / 189°
					786 above, no other clouds.
113716	R3.1e	3000ft.	026		End run.
114343	R3.2s	3000ft.	215		Run displaced from runway (10° Approach) 1018 QTH.
114410	R3.2e	3000ft.			End run climb to 5000ft.
144720		500ft.			Heirloom + camera dem calcs started
114903	R4.1s	5000ft.	030	52°5.9'N 0°53.9'E	Run displaced. 20° Approach.
114926	R4.1E	5000ft.	027		IR camera missed runway. T/TD = 5.44 / -15.75°
		5000ft.			Wind = 15ms ⁻¹ / 187°

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B250** Date 30/11/06 Name CLARE LEE Page 3 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115649	R4.2s	5000ft.	205		2nd attempt. - adjusted distance away. TITD = 5.72 / -15.92°C Wind = 14ms ⁻¹ / 187°
115725	R4.2e	5000ft.	205		End run. - reasonably good pos. ¹ (same end of runway shown on IR camera)
120207	R4.3s	5000ft.	030		Start run. - adjusted from R4
120229	R4.3e	5000ft.	029		Run end. Probs. with air traffic hence staying at 5000ft + may as well do another pass of airfield.
121040	R4.4s	5000ft.	206		Start run. displaced from runway.
121108	R4.4e	5000ft.	202		End run. Can only climb to 8000ft. now allowed to go to 10000ft.
121528		5000ft. 10000ft.			Heimann + chem cal.
121751	R5.1s	FL100)	030		Run displaced. sure good though.
121815	R5.1e	FL100)			not quite right for IR pos. ¹ TITD = -2.07 / -39.0° Winds 20ms ⁻¹ / 201°
		10000ft. on 117E2			Still clear below with 78kt above.
122030	R5.2s	10000ft.	205		(1.8 miles to right) <small>run displaced</small>
122703	R5.2e	10000ft.			End run - good in IR camera.
123259	R5.3s	10000ft.	035		Run with adjusted displacement.
123331	R5.3e	10000ft.			towards end of runway in IR camera. James happy enough good data.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B250** Date 30/11/06 Name CARE LEE Page 4 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Heading out to get profile descent.
1244					V. thin Ci over sea. ~ 518 some white caps. no Cu.
124913	P2 st	10000ft.	237	52024'N / 10336'E 52024'N / 10336'E	Profile descent. Luttscham:
					{ Vis: 35km, broken 22kft. }
					{ T/TD +10 / +7 }
					Gears down during descent
				descent speed.	5200knts at FL100
					slowed to 121 ^{knts} at 8000ft.
125640		4000ft.	225		Vis: 40km, broken 22kft. T/TD = 10° / 7°, P = 1016mb
130458	P2 end	500ft.	218		Missed approach over Luttscham climbing to 1000ft., bear up.
130850					Turning to left + descending to 500ft.
130910		500ft.			Calcs (Heiman + core chem)
					Wind 13ms ⁻¹ / 163°
					turbulence at low levels.
					T/TD 8.17° / 5.7°
131205	R6-1s	500ft.	053		Over runway
131227	R6-1e	500ft.	055		End runway
					Climbing to 1000ft to turn around.
131725	R6-2s	500ft.	223		Over grass to right of runway to right.
131751	R6-2e	500ft.	222		End run
					climb to 1000ft.
					Want to redo 1000ft to be sure have data.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.250** Date 30/11/06 Name CLARE LEE Page 5 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132040		1000ft.			Herman + chem cal.
					Wind: 14ms ⁻¹ / 168°
					T _{1/2} 6.99 / 13.79°C
132401	R7.1	1000ft.	031		displaced approach at 20°
132417	R7.1E	1000ft.	← 030		End run. Good IR images.
					Haze layer at 1000ft. (always there.)
					7/8 Ci above no other clouds.
					Ascending for transit to over sea.
132810		5000ft.	081		Chem cal.
133148					Ship spotted.
13 3239 ³²³⁹	R8.1s	4970ft.	061		Testing at this height
133315	R8.1E	5000ft.			IR camera seeing part.
					Some W to E, thin Ci above. v. small puffs.
134025	R9.1s	3000ft.	252		Passing ship L to its direction.
134054	R9.1E	3000ft.			Missed seeing it.
134527	R9.1s ^{R9.2}	3000ft.	146		Passing same ship.
134549	R9.2E ^{R9.2}	3000ft.			Ship heading 220 or 230°
135000					- Too close. - caught only in spotter.
135023	9.3s.	3000ft.			2 ships only 2nd smaller
135100	9.3E	3000ft.			one on IR camera. Goxy back
					for larger v. slow moving one.
					Leading 150° probably moved +
					just drifting.
135451	9.4s	3000ft.	103		Ship too close.
					- difficult to get good dist.
					as drifting is unpredictable.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.250** Date 30/11/06 Name CAPOE LEE Page 6 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Descending to 1000ft for smaller ship.
135729	R10.1s	1000ft.	245		Going past.
135533	R10.1E	1000ft.			Missed - too far away? Not on spotter camera White caps on sea.
140106	R10.2s	1000ft.	123		Still missed
140121	R10.2E	1000ft.			- not on spotter.
140500	R10.3s	1000ft.			Still going for same ship.
140536	R10.3E	1000ft.			
	RP.4s	1000ft.			Trying for larger original one.
140907	R10.4E	1000ft.			Missed again!
141601	R10.4s	1000ft.			large original ^{anchored} ship - going directly over the top. (will then step away to try + pick it up.)
141618					On top
141634	R10.4E	1000ft.			Even with displacement calculated by sonar, ended up on top -
142042	R10.5s	1000ft.			ship definitely drifting.
142121	R10.5E	1000ft.			
142550	R10.6s	1000ft.	241		Still missed it!
142620	R10.6E	1000ft.			
14 ³¹ 27 20	R10.7s	1000ft.	108		Try again.
143205	R10.7E	1000ft.			Missed again!
					Climbing to 3000ft.
1434		1800ft.			Passing through clouds for FSSP.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B250** Date **30/11/06** Name **CARE LEE** Page **7** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
143623		3000ft.			Clara Heermann calcs.
144011	R11.1s	3000ft.			Still same ship.
144057	R11.1E	3000ft.	279		Slightly too far away in spotter.
144519	R11.2s	3000ft.	101		Trying same ship.
144546	R11.2E	3000ft.			still missed.
					W still at East end of track, but clear over ship area
					Gi 7/8.
145028	R11.3s	3000ft.			Same ship in spotter
145132	R11.3E	3000ft.			just at of IR camera view.
					N.B. W starting to curve towards coast - hard time in interfering.
	R11.4s	3000ft.			last try.
	R11.4E	3000ft.			Still not right. Giving up.
					Transferring back to Hartfield.
~ 15:30					landing
					Problems:
					2DC - generating masses of data - switched off.
					laptop - network connection. - mouse gittering again.
					TWC - gave no data.
Suggestion on getting specific info on ship size + location. → planning in advance e.g. oil companies.					

HMS illustrious, in Southampton.
Or 1035 channel ferries? (But can't get 10kft in channel).
Harbour masters at Hull, Felixstow, Middlesbrough.

Query: Probs

Problem with 2DC? - why need switched off?
MIS laptop internet connection
mouse

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B250

Date: 30/11/06	Operator: papj	DRS Time: 07:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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SG.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
fitted	yes		yes	yes	no	yes		yes		no			yes			2dc not operated because it's creating Large data files	
	20	0.08	4													Start p1	
	25	0.08	8													090	
105227	20	0.07	8													080	
105334	25	0.08	8													070	
105454	30	0.08	8													060	
105540	50	0.08	8													050	
105758	30	0.09	8													040	
105920	100	0.09	8													030	
110105	80	0.08	8													020	
110300	200	0.08	8	10												010	
110350	500	0.08	8	10												500ft End p1	
111226	450	0.08	9	10												Start and end 1.1	
111905	400	0.08	11	10												Star and end 1.2	
113019	400	0.08	12	10												Start and end run 2.2	
113647	60	0.08	12													Start and end 3.1	
114343	60	0.08	12													Start end 3.2	
115649	20	0.08	15													Start end run 4.2	
120207	20	0.08	16													Start end 4.3 Pruge the FFSSP and it increments Block transfer by 1	
121040	20	0.08	22													Start end run 4.4.	
121751	25	0.08	23													5.1	
122630	20	0.08	25													5.2	
123259	20	0.08	26													5.3	
124913																P2	
125030	40	0.08	28													080	
125348	25	0.08	29													060	
125710	70	0.08	29													040	
130045	25	0.09	30													020	
130305	500	0.08	31	10												010 End p2	
131205	650	0.08	32	10												6.1	
131722	550	0.08	34	10												6.2	
132401	680	0.08	35	20												7.1 7.2	
134025	5	0.11	37													9.1	
134527	5	0.08	39													9.2	
135023	5	0.08	40													9.3	
135453	5	0.08	40													9.4	
135729	430	0.08	41	10												10.1	
140106	400	0.08	41	10												10.2	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B250 **T/O:** 102135
Date of flight: 30/11/06 **Land:** 152833

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B250
Date of Flight: 30/11/06

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer B250.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (B250.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B250.zip	y	Size of B250.dat =117486
6) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	Y	Blocks read =34227
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B250.dat	Y	Blocks written = 34227
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B250_seadas.dat	Y	Bad reads =0
WAVE> exit	y	
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	Y	
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	Y	
b) Flight number: B250	Y	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B250_seadas.dat	Y	
d) Comment string:	Y	
e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i>	Y	Start = 0
f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i>	Y	End = 240000
g) Read 2DC: Y	N	Ignore error message scroll
h) Read 2DP: Y	Y	(vestigial error from tapes)
i) Secondary data: Y	Y	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	Y	Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC
k) cmd.str: Y	Y	files in PMSDATA? yes
l) Auto time correction: N	N	Are they non-zero in size - y
m) Full length secondary: N	n	B250_aux.dat
8) FLOODS> WAVE		2D image display and printing
i). WAVE> imagedisplay		Must be done from FLOODS itself.
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:	No	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	images	
c) File generation no: 0		
d) Time from IWC plot: N		
e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i>		
g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i>		
h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images)		
ii). WAVE> auto_image		Note any problems with images
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD		
d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i>		Start =
e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i>		End =
f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10		
iii). WAVE> exit to create files		FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps
iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		Notes on this in instructions
v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		No images

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B250_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	<p>Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y Y</p>	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X =a Start =0 End = 240000 Time data processed to = 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat No data blocks found</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS: Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>		<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B250
Date of Flight: 30/11/06

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	Y	
Ensures B250_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	Y	
a) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	Y	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	Y	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	Y	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	Y	
d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i>	Y	Min size =1
<i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i>	Y Y	
e) Calibration volume flow rate:	Y	Vol flow rate = 1.80
<i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i>	Y	
<i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i>	Y	
<i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i>	Y	
f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i>	Y	
g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i>	Y	
h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	
3) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	Y	
ii). WAVE> exit	Y	
4) FLOODS> MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp		
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX		X =a
c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY		Y = X+1 =b
d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		
5) CHECKS		
Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter. 762</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK? yes

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 250

Date: 30 September 2006

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	N	
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann		Y	HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	N	
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	N		Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	
Upper Clear		Y	CCN / CNC	N	
“ Red		Y	CVI	N	
“ Pyrgeometer		Y			
“ JNO2	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear		Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red		Y	Nephelometer	Y	Y
“ Pyrgeometer	N		Filters	Y	N
“ JNO2	N		AMS	N	
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
MARSS	N		CDP	Y	N
DEIMOS	N		SAW	Y	N
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO2		N	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX		Y	ADA	N	N
CO		Y	CPI	N	N
ORAC	N	N	NOxy	N	
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	N	
PERCA		N	Bag Sampling	N	
WAS		N	Tube Sampling	N	

IR CAMERA FLIGHT LOG

Flight No. 250
 Date 30/11/06
 Fitted Lens 100mm
 Active NUC 05/01/2006
 BPM Filename DBTEST1

Campaign *NEON*
 Operator *SB*
 Camera Angle 35 Degs down
 Source Ref. Temp. Hot 15 Degs C
 Cold 45 Degs C

DATA RECORDING	Run	Height	Remarks
Start Time	Stop Time	Number	
	11:05:08	P1 END	MISSED APPROACH DOWN RUNWAY
	11:12:51		500ft 560ft MISS RUNWAY
	11:19:36		500ft MISS GRASS
	11:25:57	CU @	1000ft OK -
	11:30:51	CU @	1000ft
	11:37:16		3000ft
	11:44:13		3000ft DOWN @ 10° ATTACK - OK
	11:50:02		5000ft - MISS
	11:58:35		500ft - HIT BUT TOWARD 2ND END OF RUNWAY! (FORGET TO STOP)
	12:02:27		5000ft HIT
	12:11:14		5000ft - GOOD START BUT LOST STRAIGHT LEVEL
	12:18:13		10,000 - GOT FIRST END - NOT CENTRAL
	12:27:06		10,000 - FIRST HALF OF RUNWAY - BUT OK
	12:33:28		10,000 - FIRST TOP OF RUNWAY - NOT SO GOOD
	13:05:13		- MISSED APPROACH
	13:12:32		500 - DOWN RUNWAY
	13:17:54		500 DOWN GRASS - RUNWAY JUST OFF
	13:24:18		1000 - GOOD.
SHIPS - SEA STATE SLIGHTLY CHOPPY - SOME WHITE TOPS.			
	13:33:01		5000 REAR HALF OF SHIP.
	13:40:58		3000 MISS
	13:45:48		3000 MISS - ON DOWN LOOKING CAMERA
	13:50:59		3000 TWO SHIPS MISS FIRST HIT SECOND. (LARGE) (SMALL)
	13:55:13		3000 MISS
	13:57:50		1000 MISS
	14:01:28		1000 MISS
	14:05:29		1000 MISS
	14:10:54		1000 MISS
	14:16:25		1000 MISS
	14:32:04		1000 MISS
	14:40:32		3000 MISS - STEER ON TOP OF SPOTTER.
	14:45:51		3000 MISS
	14:51:34		3000 MISS - ON SPOTTER - TOO FAR BY LENGTH
	14:57:22		3000 BOW SHOT. (LONG LEAD IN...)

B250
CAL N°2

30/11/06

TARGET TEMP	INITIAL CABIN TIME
15.4	15.4706
	① min ↑ 20°C
16.7	②
17.9	3
18.8	4
19.5	5
20.2	6
20.7	7
21.2	8
22.6	9
25.3	10
27.4	11
29.4	12
31.2	13
33.0	14
34.4	15
35.4	16
36.6	17
37.7	18
38.7	19
39.5	20
40.1	21
40.6	22
40.9	23
	16 11 06. ← ?

LEFT @
20°C

LEFT @
40°C

IIR CAMERA CALIBRATION LOG

Flight No: 250
30/11/06

Operator: JSB

File Name	Target Temperature °C	Time
		08 55
	11.0	57 06
	11.0	58 06
	13.4	
	15.2	
	16.8	
	17.9	
	18.9	
	19.7	
	20.5	
	21.1	
	21.5	
	23.4	
	25.7	
	27.5	
	29.3	
	30.8	
	31.9	
	33.4	
	34.5	
	35.3	
	36.3	
	37.1	
	37.5	
	38.1	
	38.8	
	39.1	
	39.4	
	39.6	
	39.8	09 25 06

← TIME LEFT CABIN
1 min ↑
2 min 20°C
3 min
4
5
6
7
8
9
10 ↑ 40°C
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B250

Date: 30 November 2006

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS U/S
2. 2DC shut down – generating huge noise files
3. TWC flashed as expected on switch-on, multiple errors in data system u/s
4. Mission Scientist PC faulty – no comms with HORACE
5. Core Chem network comms u/s

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom H Calls - Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 30/11/06

Flight No: 6250

Pre-Flighter: JT

Item	√ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	STILL NO BIN
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	PRESSURE COLL A LITTLE HIGH @ 5.17 Bar
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	NOT FITTED.
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	TSRC PARA 74 NOT INCREASING
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	NOT WORKING SC
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NEPH &	ON & ZEROED	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
External Checks overleaf →				

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	<i>LOOKS LIKE A COUPLE OF SPOTS.</i>
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B250:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	No In Flight log (except in cases of instrument problems)
IR Camera In Flight log	IR Camera Processing log not currently available
IR Camera Processing log	IR Camera Processing log not currently available

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	17 Dec 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x spotter camera
3 x IR camera
1 x FFC/spotter
1 x Down/IR Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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